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PROSPECTS OF THE FORMATION OF CAREER DIRECTION CENTERS IN EDUCATION

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Abstract: *The article considers the issues of development of the formation of vocational research centers, including their complex planning solutions.*

Keywords: *architecture, innovation, center, creative person, profession, perspective*

Introduction: Today in the world we are witnessing the rapid growth of global competition for science and technology. It is inevitable that if someone makes a mistake in this regard, it will determine the further development of the entire humanity. A number of factors affect the choice of the type of buildings for vocational guidance innovation centers: the purpose of the building, the lack of territory, the need to combine groups of buildings intended for different functional purposes, training young people in the profession at an excellent level, the centers are determined by the need to fulfill the tasks set in place, development.

In recent years, practical work has been carried out in the Republic to support scientific and innovative activities, reform the personnel training system, special attention is paid to creating the necessary conditions for talented young people to achieve significant results in prestigious national and international Olympiads, competitions and contests, as well as vocational training. [1].

The main part: Necessary conditions for realizing the creative, intellectual and entrepreneurial potential of young people, introducing innovative ideas, projects and

technologies into production, stimulating the innovative activities of talented students, young scientists and entrepreneurs, strengthening the integration of science, education and production is being created.

At the same time, to improve the efficiency of the work carried out on the systematic involvement of young talents in the field of innovative entrepreneurship, to create a single system for talented young people to work in cooperation with businessmen and leading scientists, and on this basis, to ensure the integrity of the system of training young personnel in the field of science, to apply high technologies in the field of production, to attract young people to scientific research, and to implement scientific, technical and innovative projects it is required to create platforms for [2].

It is necessary to further revive the work carried out to support the initiatives of talented young people, to ensure the competitiveness of the country's science at the international level, to further strengthen the potential of scientific schools and to develop their innovative potential.

The history of the peoples of the Middle Ages in the East shows that the incomparable

growth in the fields of culture and education, medicine, literature, art and architecture, the creation of scientific schools, the emergence and coming of age of a new wave of talented generations - all this, first of all, was the economy. , represents that it was directly related to the rapid growth of rural and urban economy, the high level of development of crafts and trade, the opening of new highways and, above all, the stabilization of the economy. [1] [2]

In order to design a vocational guidance center in the first place, the natural climate is of great importance. In the conditions of Uzbekistan, first of all, a proposal was made to build an innovation center for career orientation in regions with a moderate climate.

A project proposal was developed for the Fergana Valley. Fergana Valley is located in a closed contour, which created the unique natural and climatic conditions of the region. Mountain ranges prevent atmospheric precipitation and cold air mass from entering the Fergana valley, so atmospheric precipitation falls 1.5 times less in Namangan region than in Tashkent. This, in turn, prevents extreme weather and winter temperature drops.

The climate of the region is sharply continental, hot and dry in summer, and relatively mild in winter. The absolute hottest amount of air temperature (+42.6°C) corresponds to July, and the lowest temperature (-23.3°C) corresponds to January. The average annual air temperature, according to long-term observations, is +14.1°C. The average annual amount of precipitation is 191 mm. Most of them fall in the form of rain in the spring months. [5] [7] [9] [10].

The proposed career orientation scientific innovation center serves to strengthen the practical application of theoretical knowledge. It can be considered appropriate to have the following general departments within the structure of vocational guidance scientific innovation centers, i.e. under them, and to take them into account when designing:

With separate buildings and experimental rooms for each direction, it is determined to create great opportunities for young people to put their professional innovative proposals into practice. Interest, motivation and final results mobilize young people to strive for innovation and creativity. When developed countries are studied, it is known that the orientation to the profession for the development of the state has risen to the level of a scientific innovation center, state policy, and practice is required from young people at the same time as theoretical knowledge.

I want to emphasize this point. Because, without peace and stability, there can be no growth and development in the field of science. Science centers, academies, and higher education institutions will appear only where there is peace and stability. The main thing is that education is developing, interest and attention to it is increasing. Only where there is peace and stability, people want to study and develop in all aspects [3].

The design of an innovation center has become the main goal of the most developed countries today, and the design of such centers is the first to introduce the country to the world [4.] [5] [6] [9].

The role of the vocational scientific innovation center and their projects is of great importance in building and establishing the great future dreamed of by young people.

Conclusion: in other words, it will be possible to know the greatness and power of our country from the modern buildings and structures that have been built and are being built, as well as unique architectural monuments. It can be said without a doubt that today in our motherland, a modern education and training system and educational facilities have been established that attract the admiration of other countries of the world. Our young people have graduated from general education schools and are studying in higher education institutions located in regional centers. These educational institutions provide an opportunity to master the secrets of the most advanced science and development, master several professions, foreign languages, Internet and information and communication technologies, and prepare mature competitive young personnel who meet the requirements of the times. The important thing is that every student who graduates from the scientific center of vocational guidance will become a mature person who is loyal to our motherland, will be ready to take a conscious step in life and find a worthy place in society.

The existence of a developed culture in the Eastern world, particularly in the life of the peoples of Central Asia, is evidenced by the monuments, mural art works and statues, and architectural examples written by the writers of ancient Bactria, Sogd, Orkhon, and Khorezm. As a proof of the above words, the architectural design of vocational training centers that teach the people of Uzbekistan from primary education to the profession in accordance with the requirements of the time guarantees not only the economy, but also a highly developed culture.

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